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Master in Data Management
and Curation

MASTER IN DATA MANAGEMENT AND
CURATION

Enhancing the Sensorium Dataset for FAIR Neuroscience Research

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Author's Declaration

I, Ana Fló, declare that this thesis entitled, 'Enhancing the Sensorium Dataset for FAIR Neuroscience Research' and the work presented therein are my own.

I certify that:

- This work was performed wholly or principally during MDMC internship in LADE.
- The Topological Data Analysis (TDA) method employed in this thesis builds upon the work initiated by Yuri Gardinazzi, Alessio Ansuini, Eugenio Piasini, Fabio Anselmi, and Matteo Biagetti. The metadata enrichment was motivated by the challenges encountered in that work.
- The FAIRification of the Sensorium dataset was conducted by me. The TDA were performed by me, based on the methods developed by Yuri Gardinazzi, Alessio Ansuini, Eugenio Piasini, Fabio Anselmi, and Matteo Biagetti. The code for TDA was developed based on code provided by my supervisor, Matteo Biagetti, with feedback and suggestions.
- With respect to AI technologies, I acknowledge:
 - the use of Claude (<https://www.anthropic.com/claude>) and Grammarly (<https://www.grammarly.com/>) for identifying improvements in writing style.
 - the use of Copilot (<https://github.com/features/copilot>) to assist in developing the TDA Python and SLURM job scripts.
- Where I have quoted from the work of others, the source is always cited. Except for such quotations, this thesis is entirely my own work.
- I have acknowledged all major sources of help.

*“Pierdo la cabeza dice
y la ve a ella, su cabeza
rodar, rodar.”*

Dina Diaz

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Abstract

The FAIR principles — Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable — provide a framework for improving the scientific value of research data. Although adoption is increasing across disciplines, neurophysiology datasets often do not meet these standards, which restricts their reuse beyond the initial study. This thesis uses the Sensorium dataset, released as part of a challenge to develop predictive models of the mouse primary visual cortex, as a case study in dataset FAIRification.

The Sensorium dataset comprises calcium imaging recordings from approximately 8,000 neurons per mouse, collected from ten mice exposed to both natural and parametrically generated video stimuli. When the dataset was accessed for a novel analysis, several essential metadata elements were found to be missing, including stimulus labels, unique video identifiers, segment-level descriptions, and data quality flags. The first part of this thesis addresses these gaps by systematically enriching metadata. A custom algorithm was developed to classify videos based on the labels reported in the associated publication. Duplicate videos within and across recordings were identified and assigned unique identifiers; equivalent video segments in parametric stimuli were detected and catalogued; and data quality issues, including missing trials and corrupted videos, were documented. All metadata was organised into a machine-readable, extensible schema using JSON and CSV formats, and released openly with a Python toolkit for data management, filtering, and visualisation, under permissive open-source and CC0 licences.

The second part of the thesis demonstrates the scientific value of this FAIRification effort by applying Topological Data Analysis (TDA), specifically zigzag persistence, to characterise the dynamics of neural population activity in response to the different stimuli. Classification analyses show that zigzag persistence vectorisations capture meaningful and generalisable topological features of neural activity. These results were enabled by the structured metadata generated in the initial phase of the thesis.

Collectively, this work highlights both the challenges of retroactive FAIRification and the scientific benefits it allows.

Contents

1	Introduction	8
1.1	The Sensorium Dataset	8
1.1.1	Neural Responses	9
1.1.2	Behavioural Measures	11
1.1.3	Visual Stimuli	11
1.1.4	Experimental Protocol	14
1.1.5	Data and metadata structure	14
1.2	Objectives	17
2	FAIRification	18
2.1	Videos Classifications	19
2.1.1	Methods	19
2.1.2	Results	23
2.2	Unique Videos Identification	27
2.2.1	Methods	27
2.2.2	Results	27
2.3	Unique Segments Identification	30
2.3.1	Methods	30
2.3.2	Results	32
2.4	Data Validation	33
2.5	Metadata and Data Management Tools	34
2.5.1	Metadata Schema	34
2.5.2	Data Managment Tools	37
2.6	Discussion	38
3	Topological Data Analysis	40
3.1	Key TDA concepts	41
3.1.1	Persistent homology	41
3.1.2	Zigzag persistence	43
3.2	Zigzag persistence for Sensorium data	43

3.2.1	Methods	45
3.3	Classification analyses	47
3.3.1	Videos' label classification	50
3.3.2	Videos' ID classification	55
3.3.3	Video segments classification	61
3.4	Discussion	63
4	Conclusions	66
4.1	The importance of FAIR data	66
4.2	FAIR by design rather than FAIRification	66
4.3	FAIRification of the Sensorium Dataset	67
4.4	Enabling Topological Data Analysis	68
4.5	Final remarks	68
A	Metadata Files Structure	69
A.1	Metadata Basic Example	69
A.2	Neurons CSV file Example	69
A.3	Trials CSV file Example	70
A.4	Global Metadata Videos	73
A.5	Global Metadata Segments	73

Chapter 1

Introduction

In recent years, research institutions, publishers, and grant agencies have increasingly advocated for open access to research data, while also promoting improved data management to maximise reusability and facilitate machine-readability as computational capacities expand. The FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) provide guidelines to improve data management. However, many available datasets fall short of FAIR standards, often due to incomplete information or the lack of appropriate ontologies and metadata schemas.

This thesis uses the Sensorium dataset [1] as a case study. The Sensorium dataset was released as part of a challenge focused on developing dynamic models of the mouse visual cortex. However, when the dataset was reused for an analysis technique distinct from those employed in the challenge, Gardinazzi and colleagues [2] encountered incomplete data and multiple issues.

1.1 The Sensorium Dataset

The Sensorium challenge aimed to develop and train artificial neural networks capable of predicting neural activity in response to natural video stimuli. Accurate modelling of neural responses to dynamic, naturalistic inputs can provide insights into visual cortex function under realistic conditions, where stimuli exhibit complex spatial and temporal statistics. Predictive coding theories suggest that the brain continuously generates internal models and anticipates forthcoming sensory information. Therefore, understanding the processing of dynamic inputs is essential for advancing knowledge of brain function. Models that generalise effectively beyond the training set may enable *in silico* experiments to probe hidden neural representations, thereby informing the design of future *in vivo* studies.

For the challenge, neural activity in the mouse visual cortex was recorded while mice viewed dynamic video stimuli. Calcium imaging with a wide-field two-photon microscope was used to record activity from excitatory neurons in layers 2-5 of the right primary visual cortex (V1). Recordings included approximately 7,000 to 8,000 neurons per mouse across roughly 720 trials or videos, each lasting about 10 seconds, resulting in a total of approximately 120 minutes per mouse. Two additional behavioural measures were collected: eye-tracking, which included gaze coordinates (horizontal and vertical positions) and pupil diameter, and treadmill running speed (Figure 1.1 A). Mice remained awake and head-fixed during the video presentation.

Although the primary objective of the challenge was to predict neural activity in response to natural video stimuli, the testing set also included five types of parametrically generated stimuli commonly used in visual research to characterise visual tuning. This addition enabled evaluation of model generalisation to these distinct stimulus types.

The dataset was released in two phases, each containing five recordings from different mice. The initial release inadvertently included the full dataset, comprising both training and testing trials. As a result, a second release was provided with five additional recordings.

The information regarding the dataset was obtained from the publication associated with the Sensorium competition [1] and the official Sensorium competition website (<https://www.sensorium-competition.net/>).

1.1.1 Neural Responses

Ten mice expressing GCaMP6s in excitatory neurons were used. Calcium imaging was performed using a Chameleon TiSapphire laser (Coherent) tuned to 920 nm and a large-field-of-view mesoscope equipped with a custom objective. A 4-mm craniotomy was performed over the right hemisphere visual cortex. Responses to a drifting bar were used to delineate visual areas. 10 planes of size $630 \times 630 \mu\text{m}$ (252×252 pixels, $0.4 \mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$) with $25 \mu\text{m}$ interplane distance in depth were recorded at 7.98 Hz (Figure 1.1 B). The most superficial was approximately $200 \mu\text{m}$ from the surface. The $25 \mu\text{m}$ interplane distance was selected to minimise the number of neurons recorded in multiple planes.

Preprocessing of the neural responses included:

1. Correction of misalignment due to bidirectional scanning
2. Motion correction of global tissue movement
3. Spiking activity estimation using the CAIMAN pipeline [3]

Figure 1.1: **A** Recording setup. **B** Coordinates of the neurons for one exemplary mouse. The 10 recording planes can be appreciated. **C** Experimental protocol showing the structure of the videos presentation.

4. Automatic neurons selection
5. Signal resampling at 30 Hz by linear spline interpolation

1.1.2 Behavioural Measures

Pupil and gaze coordinates were obtained by IR recording of the mouse's left eye. Data was recorded at 20 Hz. A model trained to detect eyelid and pupil points was used to estimate the pupil's centre and radius.

Rostro-caudal treadmill movement was measured using a rotary optical encoder (AccuCoder 15T-01SF-2000NV1ROC-F03-S1) with a resolution of 8000 pulses per revolution, and was recorded at approx. 100.2 Hz.

Behavioural measures were resampled at 30 Hz by linear spline interpolation.

1.1.3 Visual Stimuli

Visual stimuli were presented to the left eye of the mouse with a 31.8×56.5 cm (height \times width) monitor (ASUS PB258Q) with a resolution of 1080×1920 pixels positioned 15 cm away from the eye (visual angle of $3.8^\circ/\text{cm}$ at the nearest point and $0.7^\circ/\text{cm}$ at the most remote corner of the monitor). The position of the monitor was optimised by using high- and low-intensity dots in a grid, and by centring the population's receptive field within the recorded ROI on the monitor.

Videos lasted 8-10 s and were presented in grayscale at 30 Hz. The majority of videos were sampled from films and the Sport-1M dataset to cover a wide range of features and exhibit naturalistic statistical patterns. In addition, 5 classes of parametrically generated videos were used. Since they were not present in the testing set, they were referred to as out-of-domain (OOD) in the Sensorium paper [1]. The same name will be used in the current thesis. These stimuli were built by concatenating video segments. The main features of the six video classes are presented below. Figure 1.2 shows exemplary frames from each class. See Table 1.1 for a summary of the segments forming each video and Table 1.2 for a summary of the number of different videos and segments expected per class.

Natural Video 5 sets of 10s-long movies were used. A different set was used for each mouse in each released dataset. Each set included 360 videos shown once and 18 movies shown 10 times.

Natural Images Natural Images from ImageNet were used to generate the videos. Images were presented for 500 ms (15 frames), separated by a

Figure 1.2: Exemplary consecutive frames from each video class. For OOD stimuli, the shown frames straddle a transition between two video segments.

Table 1.1: Structure of the different video classes.

Class	Video length (frames)	Segments length (frames)	N Segments
Natural Video	300	n.a.	n.a.
Natural Images	300	15+[12,18]	10
Pink Noise	324	27	12
Random Dots	240	60	4
Gabor	300	25	12
Gaussian Dots	315	9	35

Table 1.2: Different videos and segments across the different video classes. A set corresponds to a group of videos. Each mouse watched one set of videos if videos from that class were shown to that mouse.

Class	# videos per set	# sets	# segments per recording	# segments total
Natural Video	540	5	n.a.	n.a.
Natural Images	6	3	60	180
Pink Noise	6	3	72	216
Random Dots	8	3	32	96
Gabor	6	3	72	72
Gaussian Dots	6	3	210	210

400-600 ms blank (12-18 frames), and each video contained 10 images. 3 sets of videos were used, and for each set, 6 videos were generated (60 different images per set, 180 different images in total). Each set was shown in 2 recordings.

Directional Pink Noise Pink noise (1-f decay in spatial frequency) with spatial orientation perpendicular to the direction of motion was generated. Each video was built by concatenating 12 segments, each lasting 900 ms (27 frames). 3 sets of videos were used, and for each set, 6 videos were generated (72 video-segments per set). All video segments were generated from different seeds; thus, they are unique (216 in total). Each set was shown in 2 recordings.

Random Dots Kinematogram Movies were generated using 8 trajectories (translational: up/down/left/right, radial: inward/outward, or rotational: clockwise/anticlockwise), 2 velocities (0.3 or 0.5 fraction of monitor width/second), and 2 coherence levels (50% or 100%). Dots' lifetime was 1s. Each video segment lasted 2 s, and 4 segments were used to build a video. 3 sets of videos were generated, with 8 videos per set (32 video segments per set, 96 video segments in total). Each set was shown in 2 recordings.

Spatiotemporal Drifting Gabor Gabor patches lasting 833 ms (25 frames) were constructed using 8 directions, 3 spatial frequencies, and 3 temporal frequencies, giving a total of 72 different video-segments. 12 video segments were concatenated to form a video. 3 sets of videos were used, with 6 videos generated per set. The videos differ between sets in the arrangement of the segments, but across all sets, the same 72 video segments were shown. Each set was shown in 2 recordings.

Gaussian Dots 210 different dots were presented –105 positions (15 horizontal x 7 vertical grid) x 2 dot color intensities (black:0 or white:255). Dots were presented for 300 ms (9 frames). 35 dots were arranged to form a single video. 3 sets of videos were used, with 6 videos generated per set. The videos differ between sets in the arrangement of the dots, but in all sets, the same 210 different dots were shown. Each set was shown in 2 recordings.

For more details about the stimuli, see [4, 5].

1.1.4 Experimental Protocol

Each recording has 4 parts with the following stimuli (for a summary see Table 1.3, Figure 1.1 C):

Training set 60 minutes of natural movies, with one repetition of each video (60 minutes total, 360 different videos expected).

Validation set 1 minute of natural movies, with 10 repetitions of each video (10 minutes total, 6 different videos expected, 10 times each)

Live test set 1 minute of natural movies and 1 minute of OOD stimuli belonging to one class, with 10 repetitions of each video (20 minutes total, 6 different Natural videos and 6/8 different OOD stimuli expected, 10 times each). Across the five recordings belonging to the same release, each recording had a different OOD stimuli class presented in this phase.

Final test set 1 minute of natural movies and 2 minutes of OOD stimuli belonging to two different classes, with 10 repetitions of each video (30 minutes total, 6 different Natural videos and 6/8 x 2 different OOD stimuli expected, 10 times each). Across the five recordings belonging to the same release, each OOD stimuli class was presented to two mice in this phase

1.1.5 Data and metadata structure

The Sensorium datasets were organised with recordings in individual folders, each containing data and metadata folders. The folder structure is schematized in Figure 1.3.

The content of the data and metadata folders was retrieved by inspection. The data folder contained four subfolders, each containing numpy arrays

Table 1.3: Expected stimuli distribution across one recording session.

Set	Duration (min)	Natural videos		OOD stimuli	
		Unique (#)	Times (#)	Unique (#)	Times (#)
Training	60	360	1	0	0
Validation	10	6	10	0	0
Live Test	20	6	10	6/8	10
Final Test	30	6	10	6/8+6/8	10

Figure 1.3: Dataset folder structure

with different kinds of data. In all cases, the file names of the numpy arrays correspond to trial identifiers.

- *videos*: It contains numpy arrays for each video presented. Each array has a shape of 36 (pixels vertical) x 64 (pixels horizontal) x # frames
- *responses*: It contains numpy arrays with the neural responses. Each array has a shape of # of neurons x # frames
- *pupil_center*: It contains numpy arrays with the gaze position. Each array has a shape of 2 (x, y position) x # frames
- *behaviour*: It contains numpy arrays with the pupil size and the locomotion speed. Each array has a shape of 2 (pupil size, locomotion speed) x # frames

While all data arrays have a fixed time dimension within each recording, not all videos lasted the full duration. An inspection of the data revealed that the data was padded with NaNs.

The meta folder contained three subfolders.

- *neurons*: It contains two numpy arrays. *cell_motor_coordinates.npy* contains the 3D coordinates for each neuron (array of shape # of neurons x 3). *unit_ids.npy* contains IDs for each neuron (array of shape # of neurons)
- *trials*: It contains a numpy array of strings with length \geq the number of arrays in data folders. The possible values are
 - nan
 - train
 - oracle
 - live_test_main
 - live_test_bonus
 - final_test_main
 - final_test_bonus
- *statistics*: it contains descriptive statistics for the different data types organised in four subfolders (*behaviour*, *pupil_center*, *responses*, and *videos*). Each contained a *all* and *stimulus_Clip* folder with the following numpy arrays: *max.npy*, *min.npy*, *mean.npy*, *median.npy*, and *std.npy*

The Sensorium dataset lacks documentation regarding the contents of the data and metadata folders, which complicates their interpretation and use. Additionally, the dataset does not specify details about the presented videos, including class membership, correspondence between trials and repeated video presentations, or, for OOD videos, the specific segments used to generate them. Although this omission may be justified within the context of the Sensorium challenge, it limits the dataset’s applicability for broader research.

1.2 Objectives

This thesis addresses two primary objectives. The first objective, detailed in Chapter 2, is to develop metadata for the Sensorium dataset to enhance its reuse and interoperability. This will be accomplished by integrating information from the corresponding manuscript [1] with generated stimulus descriptions within a suitable metadata schema. The second objective involves utilising the generated metadata to perform unsupervised analysis of the neural responses using methods from Topological Data Analysis. This analysis extends the work of Gardinazzi et al. [2], who previously examined the same dataset using incomplete and basic metadata. The results of this analysis are presented in Chapter 3.

Chapter 2

FAIRification

Standards for neurophysiological data remain limited, with development lagging behind related fields such as structural biology, genomics, and brain imaging. This lag is likely attributable to the considerable heterogeneity in data types and experimental designs [6, 7]. In recent years, initiatives have emerged to establish data and metadata standards, most notably the Neurodata Without Borders (NWB) initiative <https://nwb.org/>. Achieving full FAIRification of the Sensorium dataset would require organising it according to these principles to promote data reuse, ensure experimental reproducibility, and enable interoperability, including the application of analytical tools. However, this was not feasible due to insufficient information regarding experimental details, data acquisition, and data processing, as well as restrictions on dataset modification imposed by the CC-BY-NC-ND-4.0 license. Consequently, the present work is limited to metadata enrichment, particularly concerning the stimuli presented. Enhanced, machine-readable metadata within an appropriate metadata schema will support dataset reuse for analyses beyond those performed in the original Sensorium challenge and may also facilitate future conversion to NWB standards.

The primary steps involved in metadata enrichment are as follows:

1. Classify the videos according to the labels described in the manuscript.
2. Identify equivalent videos both within individual mice and across different mice.
3. Identify equivalent video segments for parametrically generated videos within and between mice.
4. Develop an appropriate metadata schema.

5. Develop a toolkit for validating data and metadata, managing the dataset, and providing basic data visualisation tools.

2.1 Videos Classifications

Video classification was performed leveraging the known structure of the OOD stimuli. OOD stimuli were created by concatenating distinct video segments, resulting in videos with different labels having different total lengths, numbers of segments, and segment durations (see Table 1.1). The first step in classification was to identify the start and end points of each segment. Segment boundaries were detected by measuring differences between consecutive frames, as greater changes are expected at segment transitions than within a segment. The Mean Squared Error (MSE) was used to quantify these changes, and a custom function was used to identify peaks. After segments were identified, they were characterised, since segments with different labels showed distinct, easily detectable features. For example, Natural Images and Gaussian Dot videos display static images, while Gaussian Dot, Drifting Gabor, and Random Dots share a grey background. Natural Images alternate with a grey screen. These basic descriptive properties, together with the number of segments and their duration, were used for classification.

2.1.1 Methods

Peak-detection Algorithm

Figure 2.1 presents the MSE time course between adjacent frames. Each video class displays a unique profile, with regularly occurring peaks and varying temporal patterns. Standard peak detection algorithms do not perform consistently across these scenarios, so a custom algorithm was developed. The approach uses windowed thresholding: for each sample t in the signal $S(t)$, time windows before $[t - w, t)$ and after $(t, t + w]$ are considered, and two thresholds are calculated as follows:

$$thresh_a = \max(thresh_{min}, n \times std(S([t - w, t]))) \quad (2.1)$$

$$thresh_b = \max(thresh_{min}, n \times std(S((t, t + w]))) \quad (2.2)$$

The thresholds are used to determine whether sample t is a peak based on the previous and subsequent samples:

$$isPre = (S(t) > (S(t - 1) + thresh_a)) \vee (S(t) < (S(t - 1) - thresh_a)) \quad (2.3)$$

$$isPost = (S(t) > (S(t + 1) + thresh_b)) \vee (S(t) < (S(t + 1) - thresh_b)) \quad (2.4)$$

Figure 2.1: MSE between consecutive frames for exemplary videos of each stimulus class. Red crosses indicate detected peaks. Blue dashed lines indicate detected edges between video segments.

The sample is defined as a peak if $isPre \wedge isPost$. Then, if it is a peak, prominence is computed as

$$P(t) = \max(S(t) - \max(S(t-1), S(t+1)), \min(S(t-1), S(t+1)) - S(t)) \quad (2.5)$$

Finally, if peaks closer than a minimum distance d are present, the one with the smaller prominence P is removed. Input parameters of the algorithm are: w , n , $thresh_{min}$, and d , and they were set as: $t = 10$, $n = 5$, $thresh_{min} = 10$, and $d = 7$.

Although the algorithm sets thresholds based on the variance of nearby samples, some peaks may be missed. This issue is particularly evident in Random Dot videos, which exhibit high between-frame MSE variability and only three peaks, leading to frequent peak-missing or over-detection, and misclassification as Natural Video. Adjusting peak detection parameters for specific scenarios can improve results; for example, when there is high variability and a few peaks, it is better to increase the peak detection algorithm's window size. Therefore, after the initial classification, the peak detection algorithm was re-run with parameters tailored to each label (see Table 2.1) to ensure more appropriate settings.

Another common issue is the absence of peaks when the last frame of one segment closely resembles the first frame of the next (see, for example, 2.1 Pink Noise and Drifting Gabor). To address this problem, a final check was

performed to determine whether adding a peak would yield equally spaced peaks.

Table 2.1: Parameter for initial peak detection (first row) and re-detection (subsequent rows) with parameters defined based on the label defined after the first detection.

Class	w	n	$tresh_{min}$	d
First detection	10	5	10	7
Natural Video	30	5	10	7
Natural Images	10	3	10	10
Pink Noise	10	5	10	20
Random Dots	20	5	10	45
Gabor	10	3	10	20
Gaussian Dots	5	3	10	7

Segments Description

Once peaks were detected, the beginning and end of the segments were defined, and the segments were characterised using the features below.

- *Is it static?* The maximum MSE between consecutive samples for the segment is computed, which can be referred to as *MaximumChange*. The segments are defined as static if $MaximumChange < 50$. Since it was noticed that when static images were shown (i.e, Natural Images and Gaussian Dot) segments had transition frames, in which the last frame of a segment and the first frame of the following are mixed, *MaximumChange* is also computed, removing the i first and last j frames, with $i, j \leq 3$, and the minimum i, j are considered transition frames if the condition $MaximumChange < 50$ is reached.
- *Is uniform?* Segments are considered uniform if the intensity range is below 35. This is expected for the grey frames separating Natural Images.
- *Has margins?* Left, right, top, and bottom margins are defined as the number of pixels in each direction for which the intensity range is below 35.
- *Background proportion* The proportion of background is computed as the proportion of pixels having the most represented intensity value (using 255 bins).

- *Is Uniform?* A segment is considered uniform if its background proportion is greater than 80% and its intensity range is less than 35.

Class Attribution

For the five OOD classes, it was checked whether the segment could belong to them. Different properties and segment durations were checked within acceptable tolerances. A tolerance was considered for segment durations, since, for example, transition frames can alter segment edge definitions and, consequently, durations. The number of segments matching the requirements and the total number of segments were used to determine whether a segment could belong to that class.

- Natural Images videos are required to contain only static segments, with alternating uniform and non-uniform segments. Non-uniform segments must have a duration of 15 ± 2 frames, while uniform segments (grey background) must last $[12, 18] \pm 2$ frames. The expected composition is 10 image segments and 10 grey segments. Up to 4 segments with properties outside the specified criteria are permitted, and a deviation of up to 2 in the total number of segments is allowed.
- Pink Noise videos must not contain margins and should have a total duration of 27 ± 2 frames. The expected number of segments is 12. A maximum of 2 segments with properties outside the specified criteria is accepted, and a deviation of up to 2 in the total number of segments is permitted.
- Random Dots videos are required to have a background proportion of at least 50% and a total duration of 60 ± 2 frames. The expected number of segments is 4. A maximum of 1 segment with properties outside the specified criteria is accepted, and a deviation of up to 1 in the total number of segments is allowed.
- Gabor videos must include left and right margins, maintain a background proportion of at least 50%, and have a total duration of 25 ± 2 frames. The expected number of segments is 12. Up to 2 segments with properties outside the specified criteria are accepted, and a deviation of up to 2 in the total number of segments is permitted.
- Gaussian Dots videos are required to contain static segments with a background proportion of at least 50% and a total duration of 9 ± 1 frames. The expected number of segments is 35. Up to 2 segments with

properties outside the specified criteria are accepted, and a deviation of up to 2 in the total number of segments is permitted.

If a segment met the criteria for more than one OOD class, the classification output was designated as "unknown". If a segment matched only one class, it was assigned to that class. Segments that did not match any OOD class were attributed to the Natural Video class.

Full Videos Classification Pipeline

The steps for the full classification procedure were the following:

1. Compute the MSE between consecutive frames
2. Find peaks and define the start and end of segments
3. Describe the segments
4. Attribute a to a class
5. Re-define the peaks with parameters better tuned to the label. Describe, and attribute to a class again.
6. Check for plausible missing peaks (i.e., edges) and eventually split segments. Describe, and attribute to a class again.

2.1.2 Results

For all 7145 videos analysed, a label was assigned (no "unknown" outputs). A change in class between first- and second-label assignments occurred in 39 trials, all of which were first labelled as Natural Videos and re-labelled as Random Dots after peaks were re-detected.

Only two Natural Images videos were found to have a segment with bad properties. Further exploration revealed that the grey background between images, which should last for [12, 18] frames, was displayed for more than 100 frames in one segment (Figure 2.2).

Subsequently, it was verified that the number of videos per class and their distribution across experimental phases were consistent with the paper describing the sensorium dataset [1] (see Table 1.3). Each mouse was presented with Natural Videos and videos from 3 of the 5 OOD classes, as expected. The number of trials within each video class for each mouse is shown in Table 2.2. The number of trials from each class, divided by experimental phase, is shown in Tables 2.3 and 2.4. The results generally correspond to the expected

Figure 2.2: One of the two Natural Images corrupted Videos. **A** MSE between consecutive frames. Red crosses indicate detected peaks. Blue dashed lines indicate detected edges between video segments. **B** One frame plotted over 10 frames, illustrating how a grey background was shown for over 100 frames.

Table 2.2: Number of trials within each video class for each recording.

Recording	Natural Video	Natural Images	Pink Noise	Random Dots	Gabor	Gaussian Dots
29156-11-10	523	-	59	79	-	59
29228-2-10	527	59	-	-	59	-
29234-6-9	530	60	-	-	59	-
29513-3-5	535	59	60	-	-	60
29514-2-9	528	-	-	79	58	58
29712-5-9	519	-	58	76	-	58
29515-10-12	494	58	-	73	57	-
29623-4-9	533	60	60	-	-	58
29647-19-8	539	-	-	80	60	60
29755-2-8	533	60	60	-	59	-

distribution: 540 videos for Natural Videos (360 in training and 60 in each of the other three phases) and 60 videos for all OOD classes except Random Dots, for which 80 were anticipated. Nevertheless, the observed counts were consistently lower than expected. This discrepancy suggests the presence of missing trials, which, although not explicitly addressed in the Sensorium paper, can be inferred from discontinuities in trial numbering and NaN values in the trials' metadata.

Table 2.3: Number of trials within each video class and experimental phase for each recording in the dataset 1.

Phase	Natural Video	Natural Images	Pink Noise	Random Dots	Gabor	Gaussian Dots
recording 29156-11-10						
train	350	-	-	-	-	-
oracle	59	-	-	-	-	-
live test	56	-	59	-	-	-
final test	58	-	-	79	-	59
recording 29228-2-10						
train	352	-	-	-	-	-
oracle	60	-	-	-	-	-
live test	58	-	-	-	59	-
final test	57	59	59	-	-	-
recording 29234-6-9						
train	355	-	-	-	-	-
oracle	58	-	-	-	-	-
live test	58	-	-	80	-	-
final test	59	60	-	-	59	-
recording 29513-3-5						
train	356	-	-	-	-	-
oracle	59	-	-	-	-	-
live test	60	59	-	-	-	-
final test	60	-	-	60	-	60
recording 29514-2-9						
train	351	-	-	-	-	-
oracle	60	-	-	-	-	-
live test	57	-	-	-	-	58
final test	60	-	-	79	58	-

Table 2.4: Number of trials within each video class and experimental phase for each recording in the dataset 2.

Phase	Natural Video	Natural Images	Pink Noise	Random Dots	Gabor	Gaussian Dots
recording 29712-5-9						
train	359	-	-	-	-	-
oracle	60	-	-	-	-	-
live test	60	-	-	80	-	-
final test	60	-	-	-	60	60
recording 29515-10-12						
train	348	-	-	-	-	-
oracle	58	-	-	-	-	-
live test	56	-	58	-	-	-
final test	57	-	-	76	-	58
recording 29623-4-9						
train	329	-	-	-	-	-
oracle	56	-	-	-	-	-
live test	53	-	-	-	57	-
final test	56	58	-	73	-	-
recording 29647-19-8						
train	354	-	-	-	-	-
oracle	60	-	-	-	-	-
live test	60	-	-	-	-	58
final test	59	60	60	-	-	-
recording 29755-2-8						
train	354	-	-	-	-	-
oracle	59	-	-	-	-	-
live test	60	60	-	-	-	-
final test	60	-	60	-	59	-

2.2 Unique Videos Identification

As reported in Table 1.2, the same videos were repeated up to 10 times within one recording. Moreover, mice from the first and second dataset releases were expected to have seen the same videos. To identify trials in which the same video was presented, pairwise dissimilarities among the videos were computed, duplicate videos were identified, and each set of equivalent videos was assigned a unique identifier so that two identical videos share the same ID.

2.2.1 Methods

Dissimilarity was estimated as the MSE between a subset of frames of the pair of videos being compared. Key frames were selected for each video segment. For the static segments (i.e., segments in Natural Images and Gaussian Dot videos), only one frame in the middle of the segment was considered. For videos in the other three OOD classes (i.e., Random Dots, Gabor, and Pink Noise), one frame was taken every 8 frames. For the Natural Videos class, one frame was taken every 10 frames. The videos' dissimilarity was computed using the joint key frames obtained from the pair of videos being compared.

The process for finding equal videos and assigning IDs was as follows:

1. Dissimilarity was computed for all trial pairs looping over video classes and recordings (i.e., first for video pairs in trials of recording 1 label A, then label B..., then for recording 2...). Two videos were considered the same if $D(i, j) < 5$, where $D(i, j)$ is the dissimilarity between video i and j . As shown in Figure 2.3, dissimilarity was either 0 or much greater than the established threshold. Then, sets of equivalent videos were defined using the Scipy methods *csr_matrix* and *connected_components*.
2. The videos of each set were compared with all the unique videos already identified for that label. One example from the set and one example for that ID were used. If the video in the set matched a video with an existing ID, that ID was assigned to all the videos in the set. If the videos did not match any existing ID, a new ID was assigned.

Video IDs have the form v followed by a six-digit sequence.

2.2.2 Results

A total of 1987 distinct videos were identified. Of these, 92 (approximately 5%) were exclusive to a single recording (i.e., a mouse), while the remain-

Figure 2.3: Dissimilarity matrices (left) and histograms (right) showing the dissimilarity values for all pairs of videos within each class. The videos shown to a single mouse watching the video class are presented.

ing 1895 trials appeared in two recordings, consistent with the experimental protocol, which specified that pairs of mice in the first and second dataset releases viewed identical videos.

Figure 2.4 demonstrates that mice either viewed largely overlapping video sets or entirely different sets, enabling the identification of pairs exposed to the same videos. Figure 2.5 displays the number of videos shown twice or only once to each mouse, grouped by mouse pair. Videos viewed exclusively by one mouse were limited to Natural Videos and, in two instances, to Natural Images. Further analysis revealed that these Natural Images videos corresponded to the faulty videos described in Section 2.1.2, accounting for 7 unique Natural Images videos in those recordings rather than 6. Because most Natural Videos were presented only once per mouse, missing a trial resulted in that video not being presented. These results are therefore consistent with the occurrence of missing trials.

Figure 2.4: Matrix showing the number of common videos between all pairs of recordings. It can be noted that two pairs either did not share any video or shared most of them.

Table 2.5 summarises the number of unique videos and their repetition counts within each recording. The repetition count is often marginally below

Figure 2.5: Counts of repeated and non-repeated videos across mice, separated by stimulus class and recording pair.

expectations, again, likely due to missing trials.

2.3 Unique Segments Identification

As outlined in section 1.1.3, OOD videos were generated by concatenating different video segments. Equivalent segments were identified within each label and across recordings. This process employed a method analogous to that used for identifying repeated videos, in which the MSE was calculated over key frames for pairs of segments.

2.3.1 Methods

For each OOD-stimulus video class, a representative video for each video ID was loaded, and all segments were identified. Then, the dissimilarity between all pairs of segments was computed as the MSE between their key frames. Key frames were selected with the same criteria described in section 2.2.1, except that a shift of up to +2 or -2 frames was tested, and the shift yielding the smallest dissimilarity was chosen. This adjustment was implemented because the edge definitions of segments may vary slightly between segments in videos j and i due to transitions between segments. Two segments were considered identical if their dissimilarity was less than 20. The dissimilarity matrices for segments associated with different labels are presented in Figure 2.6. The dissimilarity was zero for many segment pairs and clearly greater than zero for others. The only class without a distinct separation is Drift-

Table 2.5: Number of different videos and number of times each of them was presented within each video class for each recording.

Recording	Natural Video		Natural Images		Pink Noise		Random Dots		Gabor		Gaussian Dots	
	N	times	N	times	N	times	N	times	N	times	N	times
29156-11-10	350 12 5 1	1 10 9 8	-	-	5 1	10 9	7 1	10 9	-	-	5 1	10 9
29228-2-10	352 14 3 1	1 10 9 8	5 1	10 9	5 1	10 9	-	-	5 1	10 9	-	-
29234-6-9	355 13 5	1 10 9	6	10	-	-	8	10	5 1	10 9	-	-
29513-3-5	356 17 1	1 10 9	5 1 1	10 8 1	6	10	-	-	-	-	6	10
29514-2-9	351 15 3	1 10 9	-	-	-	-	7 1	10 9	5 1	10 8	4 2	10 9
29712-5-9	359 18	1 10	-	-	-	-	8	10	6	10	6	10
29515-10-12	348 10 7 1	1 10 9 8	-	-	4 2	10 9	4 4	10 9	-	-	4 2	10 9
29623-4-9	329 7 7 4	1 10 9 8	4 2	10 9	-	-	3 4 1	10 9 7	4 1 1	10 9 8	-	-
29647-19-8	354 17 1	1 10 9	6	10	6	10	-	-	-	-	4 2	10 9
29755-2-8	354 17 1	1 10 9	5 1 1	10 9 1	6	10	-	-	5 1	10 9	-	-

ing Gabors, likely due to residual minor misalignments between segments or improper identification of transition frames, which results in differences between segments across different videos. Each set of segments was assigned a unique identifier in the form s followed by a six-digit number.

Figure 2.6: Dissimilarity matrices (left) and histograms (right) showing the dissimilarity values for all pairs of video segments in each OOD stimuli class.

2.3.2 Results

Table 2.6 presents the number of unique segments per video class, which aligns with expectations based on stimulus construction (see Section 1.1.3). Within each recording, each segment appears approximately 8 to 10 times, reflecting the design in which each segment is included in one video per recording. Across recordings, segments are present in two recordings for Natural Images, Pink Noise, and Random Dots, and in six recordings for Gaussian Dots and Drifting Gabor. This distribution is consistent with stimulus construction, as all segments for the latter two labels were used across

all stimulus sets.

Table 2.6: Number of unique segments per video class.

Natural Images	Pink Noise	Random Dots	Gabor	Gaussian Dots
180	216	96	72	210

2.4 Data Validation

Multiple inconsistencies were identified in the dataset and documented systematically in the metadata. One inconsistency involved discrepancies between the data shape and the actual number of valid frames per trial. Although the number of valid frames varied across video classes, all videos were padded with NaNs to standardise their lengths across trials. For each recording, all trials were homogenised to the same number of frames across all data types; however, the lengths of these data types differed between recordings. Furthermore, video, neural response, and gaze data included NaNs for data beyond the valid video frames, whereas pupil and locomotion data were not padded with NaNs beyond the video’s length. The number of non-NaN frames was verified for each data type, including neural responses, videos, and behavioural measures. This information was recorded in the metadata, along with the minimum number of valid frames between the response and the video, which defined the valid frame count for each trial.

A second issue was observed in the second dataset, where the test data were never released. In its current state, the testing data consist of matrices populated with zeros. To address potentially corrupted data, a label indicating the validity of each data type (i.e., whether it contains only NaNs or only zeros) was added to the metadata. Missing neural responses were specifically labelled as invalid responses. Figure 2.7 presents the number of valid neural responses for each recording, categorised by trial type. Additionally, the two trials containing corrupted videos were marked with *valid_video* set to *False*.

A *valid_trial* label was also defined. In the current metadata, this label is set to *False* only for trials where *valid_video* is *False*, corresponding to the two trials with corrupted videos. However, this criterion could be adjusted based on alternative definitions.

The number of valid frames for videos was 300 for Natural Videos; in the range [305, 326] for Natural Images (excluding corrupted videos); 324 for Pink Noise; 240 for Random Dots; 300 for Gabor; and 315 for Gaussian Dots. Durations corresponded to expected values based on the paper’s stimulus

Figure 2.7: Number of trials with valid data for the neural responses separated by recording and phase.

descriptions, except for Natural Images, which were expected to last 300 frames, given that the image plus grey background presentation was expected to last 30 frames on average. The number of valid frames in neural responses and videos matched when restricted to valid neural responses, whereas the number of valid frames for pupil and locomotion was always higher, since these two measures were not filled with NaNs, as mentioned previously.

2.5 Metadata and Data Management Tools

2.5.1 Metadata Schema

Metadata was generated in machine-readable formats, specifically JSON and CSV. The metadata was organised into per-recording files and global metadata files shared across recordings. Global metadata regards unique videos and video segments, while per-recording metadata includes information about each recording and its associated trials. The structure of the metadata folder is illustrated in Figure 2.8. Further details regarding the metadata schema are provided below.

Figure 2.8: Directory structure of the metadata folder.

Metadata per recording

For each recording, metadata was stored within a folder named as the recording, containing the following files:

- *Basic information about the recording*: At the top level of each recording folder, a JSON file was generated containing essential information extracted from the manuscript and dataset repository README files. This information includes animal ID, session, scan index, sampling frequency, number of neurons recorded, and a URL link to the data. An example of this JSON file is provided in Appendix A.1.
- *Neurons' metadata*: Metadata for the recorded neurons was organised within a folder named *neurons*. This folder contained a CSV file listing neuron IDs, coordinates, and statistical descriptors of activity across all trials. A corresponding JSON file describing the column fields was also included. An example neuron's CSV header is shown in Appendix A.2.
- *Trials' metadata*: Information for each trial was compiled in a CSV file within the *trials* folder. Each row represents a trial and includes the trial ID, video label, video ID, and experimental phase (training, test, or oracle). Additional columns specify the number of valid frames per data type, the total number of valid frames for the trial, data type validity, and trial validity. A JSON file describing the column contents was also provided. An example trial's CSV header is shown in Appendix A.3.

The recording metadata also contains a *videos* folder with one JSON file per trial, each describing the video presented. This folder was generated during intermediate stages of metadata construction, prior to duplicate video identification, and is not required in the final metadata schema.

Global metadata

Global metadata is contained in a folder named *global_meta*, and it contains:

- *Unique videos' metadata*: In a folder named *videos* a JSON file for each video ID was created. Each file includes the unique video identifier, the label, the number of valid frames, the sampling frequency, the segments that constitute it (start and end points and segment ID), and the recordings and trials in which it was presented. An example of a unique video JSON file is provided in Appendix A.4.

- *Unique segments' metadata*: In a folder named *segments* a JSON file for each segment ID was created. Each file contains the unique segment identifier, the label, the number of valid frames, the sampling frequency, and the unique videos in which it was presented, along with its position. An example of a video segment JSON file is provided in Appendix A.5.

2.5.2 Data Management Tools

The metadata, together with the Python codes required to generate it from the available datasets, are openly available in the following repository: <https://github.com/anaflo/sensorium>. The repository also includes a series of tools to filter and visualise the data, as well as notebooks that illustrate the results of different steps in metadata generation and demonstrate how to handle the data. Codes are licensed under the BSD 3-Clause "New" or "Revised" License, while metadata was licensed under Creative Commons Zero (CC0-1.0) to maximise reuse.

Tools for managing the data and recreating the metadata are based on a Python class called **Dataset** that manages the whole dataset and provides methods for:

- filtering the data from the different recordings and trials based on values in the metadata per trial CSV files
- loading the different data types based on filtering criteria
- loading the video segments information, filtering it, and loading the segments
- checking the data consistency (i.e., that the trials are the same for all data types, that metadata for neurons and trials matches the actual data)
- checking the metadata consistency and fulfilment with the metadata schema (i.e., that all required fields are present and correctly filled in each metadata file, that all metadata files exist and are consistent with each other)
- regenerate all metadata, including videos classification, definitions of video IDs and segment IDs, and the computations of descriptive statistics for neuronal activity

Different classes were written to handle each type of data:

Responses loads and plots neural responses

Video loads, displays, and classifies videos

VideoSegment loads, shows, and describes video segments

Gaze loads and plots the gaze data

Pupil loads and plots the pupil data

Locomotion loads and plots the running speed

Neurons holds and plots the neurons' data (i.e., coordinates)

Figure 2.9 provides some examples of the data management tools. Specifically, it shows how to initialize the `DataSet` object to handle the dataset and how to load and filter the data based on the metadata.

2.6 Discussion

To improve the FAIRness of the Sensorium dataset, metadata concerning the stimuli observed by the mice and the experimental protocol were reconstructed from available sources. Information previously presented in the dataset repository and the associated paper [1] in mixed or incomplete formats was systematically organised. Additional properties of the stimuli were inferred from the videos. All metadata were then integrated into a machine-readable metadata schema.

Developing fully FAIR metadata for the dataset or designing a metadata schema extensible to all neurophysiological experiments was beyond the scope of this work and was not feasible due to the limited available information and restrictions imposed by the dataset's CC-BY-NC-ND-4.0 license. Nevertheless, the generated metadata is expected to facilitate dataset reuse and may inform the development of metadata schemas, particularly for stimulus description. The benefits of comprehensive data curation will be demonstrated in the following chapter.

Further enrichment of the metadata could include more detailed descriptions of the videos presented to the mice. For parametrically generated stimuli, video segments could be characterised by the parameters used in their generation. In contrast, natural videos could be grouped by properties such as image content (e.g., landscapes, animals, or buildings) or temporal dynamics (e.g., rate of change).

```

# Import dependencies
from ssdatam.dataset import DataSet

# initialize the object to handle the dataset, check data and metadata
folder_data = 'folder_with_data' # path to the folder with the data as downloaded
folder_meta = 'folder_with_metadata' # path to the metadata folder
ds = DataSet(folder_data, folder_metadata=folder_meta, verbose=True, check=True)

# load a dataframe with all trials metadata
ds.get_trials_metadata()
ds.trials_df

```

	recording	label	video_ID	trial	trial_type	valid_frames	valid_trial	valid_frames_video	valid_frames_response	valid_response
0	dynamic29513-3-5-Video-8744edeac3b4d1ce16b6809...	PinkNoise	v391908	203	final_test_bonus	324	True	324	324	True
1	dynamic29513-3-5-Video-8744edeac3b4d1ce16b6809...	NaturalVideo	v191606	193	live_test_main	300	True	300	300	True
2	dynamic29513-3-5-Video-8744edeac3b4d1ce16b6809...	NaturalVideo	v259199	459	train	300	True	300	300	True
3	dynamic29513-3-5-Video-8744edeac3b4d1ce16b6809...	NaturalVideo	v317244	19	live_test_main	300	True	300	300	True
4	dynamic29513-3-5-Video-8744edeac3b4d1ce16b6809...	NaturalVideo	v531838	289	train	300	True	300	300	True
...
7140	dynamic29234-6-9-Video-8744edeac3b4d1ce16b6809...	NaturalVideo	v241864	286	train	300	True	300	300	True
7141	dynamic29234-6-9-Video-8744edeac3b4d1ce16b6809...	NaturalVideo	v000453	594	train	300	True	300	300	True
7142	dynamic29234-6-9-Video-8744edeac3b4d1ce16b6809...	NaturalVideo	v420262	414	train	300	True	300	300	True
7143	dynamic29234-6-9-Video-8744edeac3b4d1ce16b6809...	RandomDots	v605412	287	live_test_bonus	240	True	240	240	True
7144	dynamic29234-6-9-Video-8744edeac3b4d1ce16b6809...	NaturalVideo	v407188	88	train	300	True	300	300	True

7145 rows × 10 columns

```

rec = 'dynamic29514-2-9-Video-8744edeac3b4d1ce16b680916b5267ce'
lab = 'GaussianDot'
trial = '475'

# get the trials for one recording and one label
filtered_trials_df = ds.filter_trials(recording=rec, label=lab)

# get the trials for one recording and two possible IDs
filtered_trials_df = ds.filter_trials(recording=rec, video_ID=['v904282', 'v664518'])

# load data for one trial
video = ds.load_video_by_trial(rec, trial)
response = ds.load_response_by_trial(rec, trial)
pupil = ds.load_behavior_by_trial(rec, trial, behavior_type='pupil')
gaze = ds.load_behavior_by_trial(rec, trial, behavior_type='gaze')
locomotion = ds.load_behavior_by_trial(rec, trial, behavior_type='locomotion')

# load an exemplar video by ID and display specific frames of the video
video = ds.load_video_by_id('v892982')
fig, ax = video.plot_frames(np.arange(90,110))

# load all the responses and videos for one label and recording (list of video/response objects)
videos, filtered_trials_df = ds.load_videos_by(recording=rec, label=lab, verbose=False)
responses, filtered_trials_df = ds.load_responses_by(recording=rec, label=lab, verbose=False)

# plot the neural responses for the first trial in responses
idx_neurosn_to_plot = np.arange(0,200)
responses[0].plot_responses_raster(idx_neurosn_to_plot, normalization='by_std')

# get the neural responses data with different normalizations
data = responses[0].get_data() # not normalized
data_norm_mean = responses[0].get_data(normalization='by_mean') # (d - mean)/mean
data_norm_std = responses[0].get_data(normalization='by_std') # d/std

```

Figure 2.9: Examples of the data management tools. First, a DataSet object is initialized to handle the dataset. Then, it is shown how to load and filter the data based on the metadata.

Chapter 3

Topological Data Analysis

Topological Data Analysis (TDA) comprises mathematical techniques that allow identifying high-order relations in data by capturing the shape of the underlying manifold from which the data are sampled. TDA has been utilised across various fields, including neuroscience, where it has been used to analyse neural activity data at both macro- and microscales (see [8]; [9] for reviews).

Initial applications of TDA focused on identifying the topological structure of the neural manifold during stimulation of specific neuronal populations. Because distinct neural populations have receptive fields tuned to values of the dimensions being encoded, specific topological structures are expected in the activity patterns. For instance, when a neuronal population encodes a one-dimensional circular variable such as orientation, a circular structure is expected; conversely, a toroidal structure is anticipated if two circular variables are encoded [10]. Different recent studies have examined the topological properties of neural population activity. Singh et al. [10] applied TDA to the activity of neurons in the primary visual cortex of monkeys and found that responses to natural images exhibited signatures of both a circle and a sphere, similar to spontaneous activity. A seminal work in the field was the discovery that grid cell modules recorded from rats freely exploring an environment exhibit a toroidal firing structure [11]. Grid cells are neurons in the medial entorhinal cortex with multiple firing fields organised in a hexagonal lattice. Cells within the same module share lattice spacing and orientation but differ in spatial phase. This configuration produces consistent activity patterns across positions on opposite sides of each hexagonal tile, resulting in neural activity that resides on a torus manifold. Additional studies have employed TDA to investigate the firing patterns of hippocampal place cells [12] and heading direction [13, 14].

Altogether, these findings have strengthened the concept of Continuous Attractor Networks (CAN), which are recurrent, stable, low-dimensional ac-

tivation modes embedded within high-dimensional neural space. Neural activity is drawn toward these activation patterns, thereby constraining it and enabling robust representations of variables [11] and potentially supporting more complex cognitive functions and behaviour [15].

In this chapter, TDA is applied with a distinct focus. Rather than characterising the topological structure of the neural manifold, the objective is to use TDA to capture dynamic patterns in neural activity within V1 evoked by various videos presented to mice in the Sensorium dataset. Under natural conditions, the brain is exposed to continuously changing sensory information. Contemporary models of brain function, such as predictive coding [16], suggest that the brain continuously predicts upcoming events and updates its internal model of the world based on sensory input, principles that apply as well to activity in the visual cortex [17]. Understanding how the brain processes dynamic stimuli is therefore essential for elucidating brain function, as evidenced by the growing interest in developing valid models to predict neural activity in response to dynamic stimuli [5]. The aim of this chapter is to assess whether TDA can serve as a valuable tool for studying neural dynamics, by capturing stable representations across different contexts.

The following section introduces key concepts in TDA, such as persistent homology and zigzag persistence, and subsequently outlines the analysis performed on the Sensorium dataset.

3.1 Key TDA concepts

3.1.1 Persistent homology

The identification of topological structures is based on the principle of topological invariance. Two objects are topologically equivalent if they can be continuously deformed into one another without cutting or glueing. For example, a circle and a square are topologically equivalent, while a sphere and a torus are not. The presence and nature of holes are fundamental properties that distinguish topological objects and are formally described by homology groups. Homology groups quantify holes of different dimensions: the 0th homology group counts connected components, the 1st homology group counts loops (one-dimensional holes), and the 2nd homology group counts voids (two-dimensional holes).

The application of TDA methods requires translating data into a simplicial complex to characterise its topological features using homology groups. A simplicial complex is a collection of simplices, where a k -simplex consists of $k+1$ points or nodes: a 0-simplex is a point (node), a 1-simplex is a line

(edge), a 2-simplex is a triangle, and a 3-simplex is a tetrahedron. A set of simplices forms a simplicial complex if the intersection of any two simplices is also a simplex within the set. This requirement ensures that if a k -simplex is included in the simplicial complex K , all its constituent simplices of dimension up to $k-1$ are also present.

A widely used approach for identifying topological structures in neural activity involves representing the data as a high-dimensional point cloud, where each point corresponds to the activity of a neuronal population at a specific time. A distance metric is established between points, and those in close proximity are connected to construct a simplicial complex. Homology groups are subsequently used to identify the topological features of the resulting simplicial complex, including connected components, loops, and voids (see Figure 3.1).

Figure 3.1: Persistent homology illustration. A) Filtration of a simplicial complex. B) Corresponding persistence diagram.

Persistent homology enables the analysis of topological features in data clouds across multiple scales by tracking the emergence and disappearance of features such as connected components, loops, and voids as the observation scale changes. The parameter δ defines the scale of observation, with points connected if $d(x, y) < \delta$. By varying δ , a sequence of simplicial complexes is generated, and the homological features of each complex can be computed. Features that persist across multiple scales are unlikely to result from noise, making persistence homology robust to noise.

A key concept here is filtration, which refers to a nested sequence of simplicial complexes generated by varying δ , where each complex is a subcomplex of the next. Formally, a filtration is a sequence of simplicial complexes K_0, K_1, \dots with $K_i \subseteq K_{i+1}$. As the filtration progresses, homological features

such as connected components, loops, and voids emerge. Persistent homology monitors the appearance and disappearance of these features and yields a persistence diagram or persistence barcode, which illustrates the lifetime of each homological feature. A persistence diagram consists of points in the plane, each representing a homological structure; the x-coordinate indicates the time of appearance, and the y-coordinate indicates the time of disappearance. The distance from the diagonal ($x = y$) quantifies the persistence of the structure, with greater distances corresponding to more persistent features. A persistence barcode presents the same information using bars, where the starting point denotes the birth of a feature and the length indicates its persistence (see Figure 3.1B).

3.1.2 Zigzag persistence

In standard persistence, filtration proceeds in a single direction, so once a simplex is added, it cannot be removed. This limitation restricts its application to scenarios in which connections form only progressively. To investigate the temporal persistence of topological features, a method that permits both the addition and removal of simplices is required, as bidirectional changes in the topological structure are expected over time. Zigzag persistence offers an appropriate framework for this analysis.

Zigzag persistence [18] is a promising tool for investigating neural dynamics, as it could provide a concise description of the temporal evolution of neural activity. The approach should be robust to noise, since stable representations are expected to exhibit long-lived features, whereas transient representations or noise are expected to live for short. Notably, zigzag persistence homology could capture structural features in high-dimensional data that are invariant to the specific locations of the features. Therefore, zigzag persistence could reveal common patterns in neural activity dynamics, even when the locations of the involved neurons differ across mice.

3.2 Zigzag persistence for Sensorium data

To apply zigzag persistence to the Sensorium dataset, a sequence of simplicial complexes needs to be defined, one per frame. This implies defining the vertices and their connections, which is not trivial. In principle, vertices could correspond to individual neurons, but this approach has different limitations. First and foremost, it is not clear how to define connections between active neurons. Second, the number of neurons is large (approximately 8,000 per mouse), resulting in a computationally expensive simplicial complex. To

simplify the analysis, a 3D grid was defined, and the activity at each cell was estimated (Figure 3.2). At each frame, cells with activity above a predefined threshold were considered active and served as vertices for a cubical complex. Connections between vertices were established based on the adjacency of the corresponding cells in the grid, with each cell having up to 6 neighbours (i.e., cells that share a face with it). Consequently, edges, squares, and cubes were incorporated into the cubical complex. This process yielded a cubical complex, $C_{k,i,t}$, for each mouse k , for each trial i , and for each frame t . A filtration was constructed by sequencing the cubical complexes for each trial, and zigzag persistence was applied to it to obtain persistence barcodes. Persistence barcodes were subsequently vectorised for statistical analysis.

Figure 3.2: Pipeline for applying zigzag persistence to Sensorium data. Neural activity is first converted into grid activity, which is then thresholded to define active cells. A cubical complex is constructed for each frame based on the active cells and their adjacency. Zigzag persistence is applied to the sequence of cubical complexes to obtain persistence barcodes, which are then vectorised for classification analyses using Turnover Rate vectorisation.

To assess whether zigzag persistence captures meaningful patterns in the data, the vectorised persistence barcodes were used in various classification schemes. Specifically, trials were classified according to the video class presented to the mouse, the video ID within that class, and the video segments within that class, both within and across mice. The results obtained using zigzag persistence were compared with those from a 3D convolutional neural network (3D-CNN) applied to the grid activity data.

A repository with the code for the analysis is available at <https://github.com/anaflo/ZigZagSensorium/tree/main>.

3.2.1 Methods

Grid activity computation

Prior to grid activity estimation, the neural activity of each neuron was normalised using min-max normalisation calculated across all trials within each recording session; thus, per mouse. Grids consisting of $15 \times 15 \times 10$ cells were defined, where the 10 cells along the z axis corresponded to the 10 planes in which neurons were sampled. The minimum and maximum x and y coordinates were used to determine the edges of the x-y grid cells for each mouse.

Grid activity was estimated using a Piecewise Cubic Spline kernel, which provided a smooth estimate of activity in each cell by incorporating activity from neurons within the cell and from adjacent cells. Grid activity was computed for each frame, resulting in a four-dimensional array with dimensions $15 \times 15 \times 10 \times T$, where T is the number of frames.

Zigzag persistence computation

To define the progression of cubical complexes over time, the active cells at each frame must be specified. Ideally, filtration would vary both the threshold (scale of observation) and time. Since this approach is computationally intensive, the threshold was treated as a hyperparameter.

Different approaches could be used for threshold selection. For example, the threshold could be fixed across all trials or set per trial. If trials differ in activity, a fixed threshold would produce varying numbers of active cells. Although variations in activation levels might be informative, they can also confound results by attributing differences to the number of active cells rather than specific topological patterns. Global activity levels across video classes indeed differ (Figure 3.3), with Natural videos, Natural images, and Random Dots consistently producing higher activation than other classes across all mice.

In this analysis, the threshold was set per trial at the 30th percentile, ensuring a consistent proportion of active cells across trials (70% of cells active per trial). Consequently, threshold values varied across trials between different video classes (Figure 3.4), reflecting differences in activation, although some discrepancies were observed. Preliminary results using a fixed threshold across all trials indicate no significant differences in classification performance compared to per-trial thresholds; however, further confirmation is required. The 30th percentile activation level was selected to yield a reasonable number of connected components, loops, and voids with sufficient persistence. Figure 3.5 shows persistence diagrams for varying thresholds in

Figure 3.3: Average grid activity across different video classes. Asterisks indicate statistically significant differences between classes (Holm's correction for multiple comparisons).

an example trial. Intermediate threshold levels (percentiles 30 and 50) produce higher H1 features without a substantial reduction in H0 components. Accordingly, the threshold was fixed at the 30th percentile for this initial analysis. Future work should investigate the effects of alternative threshold values.

After defining the active cells, a cubical complex is constructed for each frame. Zigzag persistence is then applied to obtain persistence barcodes for each trial, with the dimension, birth, and death of each topological feature (i.e., H0: connected components; H1: loops; and H2: voids).

Barcodes are subsequently vectorised using the Turnover Rate method, a specific zigzag persistence vectorisation. The Turnover Rate quantifies the fraction of features that change (births and deaths) at each frame, separately for each homological dimension (i.e., H0, H1, H2), yielding a feature vector of dimension $3 \times T$ for each trial, where T is the number of frames. Turnover Rate vectorisation is applied throughout all analyses. Further investigation is necessary to determine the impact of alternative vectorisation methods.

3.3 Classification analyses

All classification analyses employed two complementary input representations: Turnover Rate vectorisations of the zigzag persistence barcodes and the raw grid activity arrays. For videos' label classification, three classifiers were applied to the Turnover Rate vectorisations: (1) Logistic Regression (LogReg), (2) a Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) with two hidden layers of 256 and 128 units, and (3) a one-dimensional Convolutional Neural Network (1D-CNN) that treats the Turnover Rate time series of each homological dimension (H0, H1, H2) as a separate input channel along the temporal axis. For subsequent analysis, only LogReg was implemented. Additionally, a 3D-CNN was applied directly to the grid activity data as a comparative model.

The grid data, stored as arrays of shape $(N_x \times N_y \times N_z \times T) = (15 \times 15 \times 10 \times T)$, were transposed to $(N_z, T, N_x, N_y) = (10, T, 15, 15)$ before being passed to the 3D-CNN. The 10 z -planes (corresponding to the 10 recording depths) were treated as input channels, analogous to colour channels in image models, while the three dimensions over which the convolutions operated were time (T) and the two spatial grid axes (N_x, N_y). The architecture comprised three convolutional blocks with 32, 64, and 128 filters, each followed by batch normalisation and $2 \times 2 \times 2$ max-pooling, a global average pooling layer, dropout ($p = 0.3$), and a fully connected output layer.

The 3D-CNN was included as a comparative model because it operates on the same underlying grid data as the zigzag analyses but captures spatio-

Figure 3.4: Threshold values for each trial across different video classes. Asterisks indicate statistically significant differences between classes (Holm's correction for multiple comparisons).

Figure 3.5: Grid activity and zigzag persistence are presented for a representative trial (recording 26156-11-10, trial 194). The initial plot illustrates the distribution of activity across all cells and frames. Subsequent plots display the persistence diagrams for thresholds spanning the 10th to 90th percentiles of the distribution.

temporal activation patterns directly, thereby having access to the full activity pattern for each trial. The zigzag persistence vectorisation signifies huge dimensionality reduction, from $(N_x \times N_y \times N_z \times T) = (15 \times 15 \times 10 \times T) = (2250 \times T)$ to $(3 \times T)$. Thus, if the classification performance based on zigzag persistence vectorisations is comparable to that of the 3D-CNN on the grid activity, this would suggest that zigzag persistence successfully extracts meaningful topological features.

To investigate which aspects of the data each method relies on, several ablation experiments were conducted in which grid activations were disrupted using distinct approaches. Classifications based on zigzag persistence and raw grid activity are expected to be affected differently. Temporal disruptions, such as shuffling the frame order or scrambling the phase of the temporal signal, are expected to impact both methods because both rely on the temporal structure of the signal. However, zigzag persistence, which encodes the sequence of topological changes over time, may be more severely degraded by these perturbations. In contrast, spatial disruptions, such as shuffling activity across cells, are likely to impair the 3D-CNN more significantly, as it depends on the specific spatial arrangement of activation. Zigzag persistence should be more robust to spatial disruptions, since its topological features do not depend on which specific cells are active.

3.3.1 Videos' label classification

The first classification analysis sought to identify the video class presented to the mouse during each trial. Video classes varied in both the type of visual stimulus and their dynamic characteristics, including segment length and number. Consequently, both zigzag persistence and 3D-CNN analyses are expected to perform effectively in classifying video classes within an individual mouse. Cross-mouse classification serves as a generalisation test, as neural networks are susceptible to overfitting, which can obscure generalisable patterns. For instance, 3D-CNN may not generalise effectively across mice since the spatial arrangement of activation patterns might vary between individuals.

To investigate the type of information captured by each method, ablation experiments were also included. Classification was repeated both based on raw grid activities and on zigzag vectorisation after the grid activities were disrupted in different ways.

Note that the video class classification is restricted to the 5 mice in the first dataset, since the second dataset was only partially released and provided data exclusively for the Train and Oracle phases, during which only Natural Videos were presented.

Methods

Since video lengths varied across classes, the data were clipped to the shortest video/trial (i.e., 240 frames) to ensure the same amount of data was used for each trial. The classification was performed both within and across mice.

Within mouse classification schema. For each mouse, four classifiers were evaluated: (1) LogReg (4,326 parameters), (2) MLP ($\approx 219,000$ parameters), (3) 1D-CNN ($\approx 24,000$ parameters), and (4) 3D-CNN ($\approx 329,000$ parameters). The first three classifiers operated on the Turnover Rate vectorizations of the zigzag persistence barcodes, whereas the 3D-CNN operated directly on the grid activity data. For classifiers operating on vectorisations, features were standardised prior to classification using a z-score transformation estimated on the training set. The LogReg evaluates the linear separability of the topological features, MLP captures non-linear combinations of these features, and the 1D-CNN captures local temporal patterns in the Turnover Rate time series. 3D-CNN captures spatio-temporal patterns in the grid activity data.

A 5-fold stratified cross-validation scheme was implemented. Neural networks were trained using the Adam optimiser with a learning rate of 10^{-3} for the MLP and 1D-CNN, and 5×10^{-4} for the 3D-CNNs, with L2 weight decay of 10^{-4} in all cases. Training was run for up to 60 epochs for the MLP and 1D-CNN, and 40 epochs for the 3D-CNNs, with early stopping applied with a patience of 10 epochs (monitored on a stratified 20% validation split held out from the training fold). Classification performance was quantified using macro-averaged F1 scores computed across the 5 folds for each mouse. Macro-averaged F1 score is the unweighted average of the F1 scores per class, where the F1 score is the harmonic mean of precision and recall. Thus, the macro-averaged F1 score gives equal weight to each class, regardless of its frequency in the dataset, making it appropriate for imbalanced datasets, as in this case, where the Natural Video class is much more frequent than the others.

Cross mouse classification schema. A leave-one-mouse-out scheme was implemented. For each held-out test mouse, the same five classifiers were trained on data pooled from all remaining eligible mice. Eligibility required that a mouse have at least two distinct video class labels after metadata filtering, implying that only the 5 mice in the first dataset were eligible, since the mice in the second dataset had data available only for Natural Videos trials. The label space for each fold was restricted to labels present in both the test mouse and the pooled training set, so that classification

was performed only on classes observable in both, reducing the label space to 4 classes. The classifiers were trained and evaluated once per test mouse (no inner cross-validation). Neural network training hyperparameters were identical to those described for the within-mouse schema above. Also in this case, classification performance was quantified using macro-averaged F1 score.

Data disruptions. Different data disruptions were applied. The general procedure was as follows: (1) the grid activity was disrupted on a given dimension, (2) zigzag persistence and vectorisations were recomputed, (3) the classification analyses were repeated. The following disruptions were implemented: (1) temporal order disruption, in which the order of frames was shuffled, therefore disrupting the temporal dynamics of the activity, but preserving the overall activation levels and spatial activation patterns; (2) phase disruption, in which the phase of the activity was altered by Fourier transforming the activity, shuffling the phase and then inverse Fourier transforming it, which should preserve the overall activation levels and power spectrum of the activity, but disrupt the temporal dynamics of the activity; and (3) spatial activation pattern disruption, in which the activity across cells was shuffled for each trial, therefore disrupting the spatial activation patterns, but preserving the overall activation levels and temporal dynamics.

It should be noted that disruptions can be applied independently to each trial or with a shared shuffle across trials, thereby preserving commonalities across trials. For instance, in the case of spatial disruption, if the same shuffle is applied to all trials, while the specific activation pattern is disrupted, the commonalities across trials would be preserved; the same applies to temporal disruptions. Disruptions were applied per trial. Future analyses might investigate the effect of the same disruption across all trials.

Results

Within mouse classification. The results indicate that both zigzag persistence vectorisations and 3D-CNNs classify video classes above chance levels within individual mice, with 3D-CNNs generally outperforming zigzag-based classifiers (Figure 3.6). The LogReg achieved performance similar to that of the more complex MLP, suggesting that the topological features captured by zigzag persistence are linearly separable for video label classification. In contrast, the 1D-CNN performed poorly, indicating that local temporal patterns in the Turnover Rate time series do not provide informative features for video label classification.

Ablation experiments (Figure 3.7) demonstrated that temporal disruptions substantially impaired the performance of zigzag persistence vectorisations, whereas these disruptions had minimal effect on 3D-CNNs operating on grid activities, as classification could still be inferred from spatial differences between classes. Notably, phase-shuffling disruptions had a more pronounced impact on zigzag persistence classifiers than frame shuffling. This may be because phase shuffling alters the definition of active grids, thereby eliminating the data’s topological structure. In contrast, spatial disruptions had a greater effect on 3D-CNN performance and a lesser impact on zigzag persistence vectorisations, indicating that zigzag persistence captures topological features that are more resilient to spatial perturbations. Spatial shuffling alters the definition of neighbouring grids inconsistently across trials. The sustained high performance of zigzag persistence classifiers following spatial shuffling suggests that the topological features identified by zigzag persistence for video label classification remain robust despite changes in the spatial arrangement of active grids.

Figure 3.6: Macro-averaged F1 score for the within-mouse video-label classification. On the left, the classifiers’ performance for each mouse is shown. Error bars represent the standard deviation across folds. On the right, performance is averaged across mice. Error bars represent the standard deviation across mice. Chance performance is indicated by a dashed line.

Cross mouse classification. The cross-mice classification results (Figure 3.8) demonstrated superior performance of zigzag persistence vectorisations compared to 3D-CNNs. This finding indicates that zigzag persistence effec-

Figure 3.7: Macro-averaged F1 score for the within-mouse video labels classification performed on data with different shuffle ablations: time shuffle (top), phase shuffle (middle), and spatial shuffle (bottom). On the left, the performance for each mouse is shown. Error bars represent the standard deviation across folds. On the right, performance is averaged across mice. Error bars represent the standard deviation across mice. Chance performance is indicated by a dashed line.

tively abstracts topological features of neural activity dynamics that are consistent across mice, whereas 3D-CNNs may depend more on spatial patterns that vary between individuals. As for within-mouse classification, LogReg performed comparably to the more complex MLP.

Ablation experiments (Figure 3.9) revealed that temporal disruptions significantly impaired the performance of all classifiers, whereas spatial disruption had minimal effect. This outcome suggests that cross-mouse label classification relies primarily on temporal patterns. For within-mouse classification, phase shuffling had a greater impact on zigzag persistence classifiers than frame shuffling. In contrast, frame shuffling affected the 3D-CNN classifier more, while phase shuffling had little impact. These results imply that preserving the power spectrum while altering the temporal structure may provide sufficient information for classification. Nevertheless, conclusions about differences between disruptions should be interpreted with caution, as multiple shuffles should be performed to obtain a performance distribution for each disruption type and to assess statistical significance.

Figure 3.8: Macro-averaged F1 score for the cross-mouse video labels classification. On the left, the classifiers’ performance for each left-out mouse is shown. On the right, performance is averaged across left-out mice. Error bars represent the standard deviation across left-out mice. Chance performance is indicated by a dashed line.

3.3.2 Videos’ ID classification

The results indicate that zigzag perspective vectorisations effectively capture topological patterns in neural activity dynamics, enabling classification of the

Figure 3.9: Macro-averaged F1 score for the cross-mouse video labels classification performed on data with different shuffle ablations: time shuffle (top), phase shuffle (middle), and spatial shuffle (bottom). On the left, the performance for each left-out mouse is shown. On the right, performance is averaged across left-out mice. Error bars represent the standard deviation across left-out mice. Chance performance is indicated by a dashed line.

video class presented to the mouse. However, video classes differ not only in the content of the video segments used to generate OOD stimuli, but also in the length and number of these segments. Consequently, it is possible that the topological features captured by zigzag persistence are limited to these patterns rather than to dynamics specific to the videos' content. To address this concern, a more fine-grained classification analysis was conducted to identify the specific video ID within each video class. OOD videos within the same class share general structural features, including the number and length of segments, but differ in specific content. Notably, the successful classification of unique Natural Videos would suggest that zigzag persistence can capture specific dynamic patterns in natural stimuli with complex spatial and temporal structure.

Methods

For this analysis, trials belonging to each video class were clipped to the expected duration of the videos in that class (i.e., Natural Videos: 300 frames; Natural Images: 300 frames; Pink Noise: 324 frames; Random Dots: 240 frames; Gabor: 300 frames; Gaussian Dots: 315 frames)

The classification analysis was performed independently per video class (NaturalVideo, NaturalImages, PinkNoise, RandomDots, Gabor, Gaussian-Dot). Only repeated video IDs were considered, as shown in Chapter 2, repeated videos appear 7 to 10 times. A reduced set of two classifiers was used: Logistic Regression operating on Turnover Rate vectorisations, and the 3D-CNN on raw grid activity. The neural network training hyperparameters were identical to those described for video class classification.

Both within-mouse and cross-mouse classification analyses were performed. However, the cross-mouse analysis was restricted to the Natural Videos. This is because while datasets 1 and 2 included pairs of mice that viewed approximately the same videos, dataset 2 only provided data for the Train and Oracle phases. Therefore, the cross-mouse analysis was limited to the 6 Natural Videos, which were presented approximately 10 times during the Oracle phase.

Within mouse video ID classification schema. A leave-one-trial-out cross-validation scheme was applied: each fold held out one trial, with all remaining trials used for training. This ensures that no information from the same trial appears in both training and test sets. Since the class frequencies were balanced, classification performance was quantified using accuracy, computed as the proportion of correctly classified trials across folds.

Cross mouse video ID classification schema. Classification was performed as a directed pairwise experiment: for every ordered pair of eligible mice (A, B), classifiers were trained on the source mouse (A) and evaluated on the target mouse (B), and both directions ($A \rightarrow B$ and $B \rightarrow A$) were assessed. All trials from the source mouse served as the training set and all trials from the target mouse as the test set, without any inner cross-validation. Also, in this case, classification performance was quantified using accuracy.

Results

Within mouse classification. Both logistic regression applied to zigzag vectorisations and 3D-CNN on grid activity classified video IDs above chance levels. However, classification based on zigzag vectorisations demonstrated superior performance across all video classes (Figure 3.10). Although the 3D-CNN has access to the full grid activity data, it may struggle to learn the complex spatio-temporal patterns associated with specific video IDs, especially given the limited number of training samples per video ID. In contrast, LogReg on zigzag vectorisations may be more effective at capturing the topological features of neural activity dynamics specific to each video ID, thereby improving classification performance.

It should be noted that the 3D-CNN classifier's performance was much better for Natural Video classification on the first dataset than on the second. The videos shown to the first and second datasets were the same; however, only videos from the Oracle phase could be included for the second dataset, whereas for dataset 1, 12 other videos that were presented repeatedly during testing were also included. Future work should investigate whether the difference is related to video variability, mouse-related effects, or the number of classes to be classified.

Cross mouse classification. Cross-mice classification of video IDs within the Natural Video class resulted in above-chance performance for logistic regression applied to zigzag vectorisations. In contrast, the 3D-CNN on grid activity performed close to chance level for all except one train/test mice pair (Figure 3.11). These findings extend the within-mouse results by demonstrating that zigzag persistence not only captures meaningful features in the activation dynamics with limited data, but also that these features are shared across mice.

Figure 3.10: Accuracy for the within-mouse video ID classification. The LogReg (left) and 3D-CNN (centre) accuracies for each mouse and each video label are shown. On the right, the average performance across mice is shown. Error bars represent the standard deviation across mice. Chance performance is indicated by a dashed line. Note that the Natural Video label is the only one with data available for the mice in the second dataset. The number of different video IDs per class are: 6 for Natural Videos in Dataset 2, 18 for Natural Videos in Dataset 1, 6 for Natural Images, 6 for Pink Noise, 8 for Random Dots, 6 for Gabor, and 6 for Gaussian Dots. Each unique video was repeated approximately 10 times.

Figure 3.11: Accuracy for the cross-mouse video ID classification within the Natural Video label. On the left, the classifiers' performance for each pair of mice in both directions is shown. On the right, performance is averaged across pairs. Error bars represent the standard deviation across pairs. Each unique video was repeated approximately 10 times. Chance performance is indicated by a dashed line.

3.3.3 Video segments classification

The video segment classification aimed to determine whether the identity of individual parametric segments within a video class could be decoded from neural activity. Video segments are substantially shorter than full videos, ranging from 9 frames for Gaussian Dots to 60 frames for Random Dots. The number of repetitions per segment is limited (approximately 10), while the number of unique segments is relatively large (ranging from 32 for Random Dots to 210 for Gaussian Dots). Despite these challenging conditions, within-mouse classification above chance might be achieved by the 3D-CNN operating on grid activity, as video segments within a class were generated parametrically along dimensions known to be encoded by V1. Classification performance based on the Turnover Rate zigzag persistence vectorisation is expected to be lower, since individual video segments lack a rich temporal structure and, consequently, neural activity is not expected to exhibit such structure.

Methods

As in the videos' ID classification, trials were clipped to the expected duration for each video class. Each trial was subsequently divided into non-overlapping segments of fixed length, determined by the temporal structure of the stimulus: Natural Images (15 frames), PinkNoise (27 frames), RandomDots (60 frames), Gabor (25 frames), and GaussianDot (9 frames). Classification was conducted independently for each video class. The same two classifier types used in the video ID analyses were employed: logistic regression for zigzag persistence and 3D-CNN for grid activity.

Both within-mouse and cross-mouse classification analyses were conducted. The cross-mouse analysis was limited in this instance as well because complete data were not available for the second dataset. Only the five mice in the first dataset had data available for OOD stimuli. Within this dataset, segment repetition across mice occurred only for the Gaussian Dots and Gabor classes, thereby restricting the cross-mouse analysis to these classes.

Within mouse segment classification schema. For each mouse and video class, a leave-one-group-out cross-validation scheme was applied based on trial ID. In each fold, all segments from one trial served as the test set, while the remaining segments from other trials were used for training. Classification performance was quantified using accuracy.

Cross mouse segment classification schema. A leave-one-mouse-out scheme was implemented. For each held-out test mouse, classifiers were trained on pooled segment samples from all other eligible mice and evaluated on the test mouse. In each fold, the label space was restricted to segment IDs shared between the test mouse and the training pool. Classification performance was quantified using accuracy.

Results

Within mouse classification. Within-mouse video segment classification results (Figure 3.12) demonstrated above-chance performance for both classifiers; however, the 3D-CNN applied to grid activity substantially outperformed logistic regression on zigzag vectorisations across all video classes. This outcome aligns with the expectation that neural responses to the video segments lack complex temporal dynamics. The strong performance of the 3D-CNN, despite the large number of classes and limited samples per class, indicates that when spatial patterns are critical for classification, the 3D-CNN can effectively learn these patterns even with constrained data.

Figure 3.12: Accuracy for the within-mouse video segment ID classification. The LogReg (left) and 3D-CNN (centre) accuracies for each mouse and each video label (only OOD stimuli) are shown. On the right, the average performance across mice is shown. Error bars represent the standard deviation across mice. Chance performance is indicated by a dashed line. The numbers of different video segment IDs are: 60 for Natural Images, 72 for Pink Noise, 32 for Random Dots, 72 for Gabor, and 210 for Gaussian Dots. Each unique segment was repeated approximately 10 times.

Cross mouse classification. Cross-mouse video segment classification results (Figure 3.13) show that the classifier based on zigzag persistence vectorisations performed at chance level, whereas the 3D-CNN applied to grid

activity achieved above-chance performance for both Gabor and Gaussian Dots segments. The 3D-CNN’s ability to generalise classification to previously unseen mice indicates that the spatial neural activity patterns underlying different video segments are consistent across mice for these segment types.

Figure 3.13: Accuracy for the cross-mouse video ID classification restricted to the Gabor and Gaussian Dots labels. On the left, the classifiers’ performance for each left-out mouse. On the right, performance is averaged across left-out mice. Error bars represent the standard deviation across left-out mice. Each unique segment was repeated approximately 10 times. Chance performance is indicated by a dashed line (72 classes for Gabor and 210 for Gaussian Dot).

3.4 Discussion

This chapter investigates the capability of zigzag persistence to capture meaningful topological features in the dynamics of activation in the mouse primary visual cortex during visual stimulus presentation. A pipeline was implemented to transform single-neuron activity into a 3D grid representation over time, followed by zigzag persistence. Subsequently, the metadata constructed in Chapter 2 was utilised to plan and conduct classification analyses.

The classification results indicate that zigzag persistence vectorisations capture meaningful features in neural activity dynamics, enabling accurate classification of both video labels and video IDs within classes. Notably,

zigzag persistence vectorisations outperformed 3D-CNNs applied to raw grid activity in cross-mouse classification analyses and in classifying video IDs within a class. These findings demonstrate that zigzag persistence abstracts topological features of neural activity dynamics that are both shared across mice and specific to video content. Crucially, this is accomplished through substantial dimensionality reduction, reducing the data from a 2250-dimensional grid activity vector per frame to a 3-dimensional Turnover Rate vector per frame, and employing a classifier with significantly fewer parameters (i.e., logistic regression rather than a 3D-CNN).

Ablation experiments provided insights into the type of information captured by each method. Temporal disruptions had a greater impact on zigzag persistence classifiers, whereas spatial disruptions had a more significant impact on 3D-CNNs. These results suggest that zigzag persistence captures topological features that are more resilient to spatial perturbations, while 3D-CNNs rely more heavily on specific spatial activation patterns.

The results presented in this chapter extend the work of Gardinazzi et al. [2]. In this thesis, zigzag persistence was applied to a 3D grid representation of neural activity, rather than computing zigzag persistence separately for each of ten planes and concatenating the results. A 3D-CNN was also applied directly to the grid activity as a comparative model, and classification analyses were conducted using complete metadata. Classification was performed using accurate video labels across six classes (Natural Videos, Natural Images, Pink Noise, Random Dots, Drifting Gabor, and Gaussian Dots), whereas previous work used only four labels (naturalistic, gaussian, waves, and moving dot). Notably, the 'naturalistic' category previously included both natural videos and natural images, which are distinct since the latter lack dynamic content. Random Dots were excluded from the prior analysis due to issues with video length. Furthermore, video duplicates were not fully detected, and video segments were not considered in the previous analysis. The current analysis also included cross-mouse classification, which was not performed in the previous work.

Although the current analysis provides initial evidence for the significance of the topological features captured by zigzag persistence, it remains incomplete and preliminary. Further investigation is required to assess the impact of different threshold values for defining active cells and to evaluate alternative vectorisation methods on classification performance. Ablation experiments should be expanded to include multiple shuffles for each disruption type, enabling the generation of classification performance distributions and the assessment of significant differences between disruptions. Additionally, other disruption types could be explored, such as applying the same disruptions with shared shufflings across trials or implementing new types of

temporal perturbations.

The specific nature of the topological features extracted by zigzag persistence remains unclear. Future research should aim to elucidate how these features relate to underlying neural dynamics and stimulus properties, thereby enhancing interpretability.

Another important direction for future research is the development of pipelines that enable the application of zigzag persistence directly to raw neural activity data, eliminating the need for an intermediate grid representation. This approach presents significant challenges, as it requires defining frame-by-frame connectivity between neurons. However, it would facilitate the capture of topological features at the level of individual neurons, potentially providing a more accurate representation of underlying neural dynamics.

The developed pipeline and analyses establish a framework that can be applied to other datasets. For example, application to fMRI data, which is inherently structured in a grid format, represents a promising direction. Abstracting topological features of human brain activity dynamics may contribute to understanding cognitive processes and to the development of neural markers for neurological and psychiatric disorders, with potential clinical applications.

In summary, the topological data analysis conducted in this chapter demonstrates promising potential for zigzag persistence in analysing neural activity dynamics and identifies several avenues for future research.

Chapter 4

Conclusions

4.1 The importance of FAIR data

The exponential growth of scientific data, combined with increasingly powerful computational tools, presents an unprecedented opportunity to extract new knowledge through data reuse, aggregation, and cross-study analysis. However, these opportunities are contingent upon data being genuinely reusable rather than simply available. The FAIR principles — Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable — provide a concrete framework for maximising the scientific value of research data by ensuring that both humans and machines can efficiently discover, access, integrate, and reuse it effectively [19].

The Sensorium dataset offers a compelling illustration of the gap between data availability and data reusability. Despite being publicly released with an accompanying paper, the dataset lacked the structured metadata necessary to support analyses beyond those originally conceived by the Sensorium challenge. While some stimulus information could not be released for the challenge, it could have been integrated later. Moreover, key information — such as mouse identifiers, data structure, and content — was either absent, scattered across heterogeneous sources, or encoded in formats unsuitable for programmatic access. As a consequence, reusing the dataset for a novel analysis required a substantial preliminary effort to reconstruct and organise missing information.

4.2 FAIR by design rather than FAIRification

The work in this thesis highlights a broader challenge in science: making data FAIR *after* it has been collected and released is a labour-intensive, error-

prone process that can only partially compensate for the absence of proper data management practices from the outset. Retroactive FAIRification is limited by the information that survives in the published record and by the impossibility of recovering details that were never documented. In the case of the Sensorium dataset, the CC-BY-NC-ND-4.0 license further constrained what modifications could be made, restricting the present work to metadata enrichment rather than full dataset reorganisation.

The neurophysiology community has increasingly recognised the need to adopt FAIR data practices. Initiatives such as the Neurodata Without Borders (NWB) standard [6] and the expanding ecosystem of tools supporting FAIR neurophysiology data [7] constitute significant progress toward this goal.

4.3 FAIRification of the Sensorium Dataset

Despite the constraints described above, the metadata enrichment performed in this work significantly advances the FAIRness of the Sensorium dataset along all four FAIR dimensions.

Findability. Trial-level metadata files containing labelled videos and unique video identifiers substantially enhance the findability of specific stimuli within the dataset. Researchers can now query the metadata to identify trials associated with specific experimental conditions.

Accessibility. All metadata generated in this study, along with the code necessary for reproduction, are openly available in a public repository (<https://github.com/anaflo/sensorium>). The code is licensed under the permissive BSD 3-Clause license, and the metadata is released under Creative Commons Zero (CC0-1.0), thereby maximising reusability and eliminating barriers to access. The accompanying data management tools further reduce the access threshold by offering high-level interfaces for filtering, loading, and visualising the data.

Interoperability. Metadata was generated in machine-readable formats — JSON and CSV — with accompanying JSON descriptor files that document the schema and field semantics. Moreover, the metadata schema was designed with interoperability in mind, using clear and consistent field names, data types, and structures that facilitate integration with other datasets and tools.

Reusability. The enriched metadata substantially enhances the reusability of the dataset. The metadata includes information on stimulus labels, video identifiers, segment boundaries, experimental phases, data validity, and the number of valid frames per data type. Neuron-level metadata provides spatial coordinates and descriptive statistics of activity across trials in a clear metadata schema. Collectively, these metadata fields enable researchers to conduct fine-grained data selection, replicate the analyses presented in this thesis, and design new analyses with precise control over included trials and stimuli. Importantly, documenting data quality issues, such as missing trials, corrupted videos, and the presence of nan- and zero-padded data, significantly enhances reusability by preventing the inadvertent inclusion of invalid data.

4.4 Enabling Topological Data Analysis

The practical value of the FAIRification work was demonstrated in Chapter 3, which utilised zigzag persistence, a method from Topological Data Analysis, to characterise the dynamics of neural activity in the mouse primary visual cortex in response to diverse visual stimuli.

Accurate trial-level metadata was essential at multiple stages of the Topological Data Analysis pipeline. Stimulus labels were necessary for establishing meaningful classification experiments. Video identifiers enabled the design of within-class classification analyses both within and across mice that extended beyond broad stimulus categories. Segment identifiers facilitated the assessment of neural decodability at the level of individual parametric video segments. Data validity flags ensured that analyses were limited to trials with intact neural responses and videos.

4.5 Final remarks

The work presented in this thesis illustrates both the challenges and the rewards of investing in data FAIRification. The metadata enrichment performed here, while limited by the constraints of a retroactive curation effort, enabled a richer and more rigorous scientific analysis than would otherwise have been possible. Future work on the Sensorium dataset could extend the metadata by characterising the content of natural videos and parametric segments in terms of their generative parameters, and by exploring conversion to the NWB standard to facilitate integration with other neurophysiology datasets.

Appendix A

Metadata Files Structure

A.1 Metadata Basic Example

An example of a metadata file containing basic information about each recording is presented in Table A.1. The file was named *meta-basic_<recording_name>.json*.

```
{
  "animal_id": "29156",
  "session": "11",
  "scan_idx": "10",
  "n_trials": 720,
  "samples_per_trial": 324,
  "n_neurons": 7440,
  "sampling_freq": 30,
  "dataset_url": "https://gin.g-node.org/...",
  "data_url": "https://gin.g-node.org/..."
}
```

Table A.1: Example of a basic metadata JSON file

A.2 Neurons CSV file Example

In Table A.2 an example of the first rows of a CSV file of neurons' metadata is presented. The file was named *meta-neurons_<recording_name>.json*.

Note that the column names were abbreviated to fit into the page; real names are:

- *ID*,
- *coord_x*,
- *coord_y*,
- *coord_z*,
- *mean_activation*,
- *min_activation*,
- *max_activation*,
- *std_activation*

ID	Coord X	Coord Y	Coord Z	Mean Act.	Min Act.	Max Act.	Std Act.
1	-1033	-700	275	1.21	-1.48e-08	63.71	2.77
2	-981	-704	275	0.83	-6.57e-09	89.11	2.88
3	-951	-704	275	0.75	-4.22e-10	69.28	2.78
4	-908	-685	275	0.55	-1.23e-09	75.23	2.52
5	-928	-690	275	0.57	-4.27e-10	100.65	2.26

Table A.2: Example of a CSV neurons' metadata file

A.3 Trials CSV file Example

In Table A.3 an example of the first rows of a CSV file of trials' metadata is presented. The file was named *meta-trials_<recording_name>.json*.

Note that the column names were abbreviated to fit into the page. Real names are:

- *recording*,
- *label*,
- *trial*,
- *trial_type*,
- *video_ID*,

- *valid_frames,*
- *valid_trial,*
- *valid_frames_video,*
- *valid_frames_response,*
- *valid_frames_pupil,*
- *valid_frames_gaze,*
- *valid_frames_locomotion,*
- *valid_video,*
- *valid_response,*
- *valid_pupil,*
- *valid_gaze,*
- *valid_locomotion.*

recording	label	trial	trial type	video ID	valid frames	valid trial	valid frames video	valid frames response	valid frames pupil	valid frames gaze	valid frames locomotion	valid video	valid response	valid pupil	valid gaze	valid loco.
dynamic29156-11-10...	NaturalVideo	203	train	v657206	300	True	300	300	324	300	324	True	True	True	True	True
dynamic29156-11-10...	NaturalVideo	193	oracle	v275212	300	True	300	300	324	300	324	True	True	True	True	True
dynamic29156-11-10...	GaussianDot	459	final test bonus	v508706	315	True	315	315	324	315	324	True	True	True	True	True
dynamic29156-11-10...	NaturalVideo	19	live test main	v484679	300	True	300	300	324	300	324	True	True	True	True	True
dynamic29156-11-10...	GaussianDot	289	final test bonus	v461218	315	True	315	315	324	315	324	True	True	True	True	True
dynamic29156-11-10...	RandomDots	25	final test bonus	v848761	240	True	240	240	324	240	324	True	True	True	True	True

Table A.3: Example of a CSV trials' metadata file.

A.4 Global Metadata Videos

An example of a metadata file for a unique video is presented in table [A.4](#). The file was named *<label>-<video_ID>.json*.

A.5 Global Metadata Segments

An example of a metadata file for a unique segment is presented in table [A.5](#). The file was named *<label>-<segment_ID>.json*.

```

{
  "label": "RandomDots",
  "ID": "v739599",
  "valid_frames": 240,
  "sampling_freq": 30,
  "segments": {
    "frame_start": [
      0,
      60,
      120,
      180
    ],
    "frame_end": [
      60,
      120,
      180,
      240
    ],
    "bad_properties": [
      false,
      false,
      false,
      false
    ],
    "segment_ID": [
      "s297253",
      "s209235",
      "s796780",
      "s347528"
    ]
  }
},
"duplicates": {
  "dynamic29623-4-9-...": {
    "trials": [
      "268",
      "426",
      "306",
      "535",
      "231",
      "488",
      "409",
      "305",
      "562",
      "2"
    ],
    "n": 10
  },
  "dynamic29234-6-9-...": {
    "trials": [
      "221",
      "384",
      "289",
      "402",
      "255",
      "558",
      "533",
      "475",
      "2",
      "290"
    ],
    "n": 10
  }
}
}

```

Table A.4: Example of a unique video metadata JSON file

```
{
  "ID": "s297253",
  "label": "RandomDots",
  "sampling_freq": 30,
  "valid_frames": 60,
  "duplicates": {
    "v739599": {
      "segment_index": [
        0
      ],
      "n": 1
    }
  }
}
```

Table A.5: Example of a unique video segment metadata JSON file

Bibliography

- [1] P. Turishcheva, P. G. Fahey, L. Hansel, R. Froebe, K. Ponder, M. Vystrčilová, K. F. Willeke, M. Bashiri, E. Wang, Z. Ding, A. S. Tolias, F. H. Sinz, and A. S. Ecker, “The Dynamic Sensorium competition for predicting large-scale mouse visual cortex activity from videos,” July, 2024.
- [2] Y. Gardinazzi, A. Ansuini, E. Piasini, F. Anselmi, and M. Biagetti, “Zigzag Persistence of Neural Responses to Time-Varying Stimuli,” Mar., 2026.
- [3] A. Giovannucci, J. Friedrich, P. Gunn, J. Kalfon, B. L. Brown, S. A. Koay, J. Taxidis, F. Najafi, J. L. Gauthier, P. Zhou, B. S. Khakh, D. W. Tank, D. B. Chklovskii, and E. A. Pnevmatikakis, “CaImAn an open source tool for scalable calcium imaging data analysis,” *eLife* **8** (Jan., 2019) e38173.
- [4] J. A. Bae, M. Baptiste, M. R. Baptiste, C. A. Bishop, A. L. Bodor, D. Brittain, V. Brooks, J. Buchanan, D. J. Bumbarger, M. A. Castro, B. Celii, E. Cobos, F. Collman, N. M. da Costa, B. Danskin, S. Dorkenwald, L. Elabbady, P. G. Fahey, T. Fliss, E. Froudarakis, J. Gager, C. Gamlin, W. Gray-Roncal, A. Halageri, J. Hebditch, Z. Jia, E. Joyce, J. Ellis-Joyce, C. Jordan, D. Kapner, N. Kemnitz, S. Kinn, L. M. Kitchell, S. Koolman, K. Kuehner, K. Lee, K. Li, R. Lu, T. Macrina, G. Mahalingam, J. Matelsky, S. McReynolds, E. Miranda, E. Mitchell, S. S. Mondal, M. Moore, S. Mu, T. Muhammad, B. Nehoran, E. Neace, O. Ogedengbe, C. Papadopoulos, S. Papadopoulos, S. Patel, G. J. Y. P. Vega, X. Pitkow, S. Popovych, A. Ramos, R. C. Reid, J. Reimer, P. K. Rivlin, V. Rose, Z. M. Sauter, C. M. Schneider-Mizell, H. S. Seung, B. Silverman, W. Silversmith, A. Sterling, F. H. Sinz, C. L. Smith, R. Swanstrom, S. Suckow, M. Takeno, Z. H. Tan, A. S. Tolias, R. Torres, N. L. Turner, E. Y. Walker, T. Wang, A. Wanner, B. A. Wester, G. Williams, S. Williams,

- K. Willie, R. Willie, W. Wong, J. Wu, C. Xu, R. Yang, D. Yatsenko, F. Ye, W. Yin, R. Young, S.-c. Yu, D. Xenos, C. Zhang, and The MICrONS Consortium, “Functional connectomics spanning multiple areas of mouse visual cortex,” *Nature* **640** no. 8058, (Apr., 2025) 435–447.
- [5] E. Y. Wang, P. G. Fahey, Z. Ding, S. Papadopoulos, K. Ponder, M. A. Weis, A. Chang, T. Muhammad, S. Patel, Z. Ding, D. Tran, J. Fu, C. M. Schneider-Mizell, N. M. da Costa, R. C. Reid, F. Collman, N. M. da Costa, K. Franke, A. S. Ecker, J. Reimer, X. Pitkow, F. H. Sinz, and A. S. Tolias, “Foundation model of neural activity predicts response to new stimulus types,” *Nature* **640** no. 8058, (Apr., 2025) 470–477.
- [6] O. Rübél, A. Tritt, R. Ly, B. K. Dichter, S. Ghosh, L. Niu, P. Baker, I. Soltesz, L. Ng, K. Svoboda, L. Frank, and K. E. Bouchard, “The Neurodata Without Borders ecosystem for neurophysiological data science,” *eLife* **11** (Oct., 2022) e78362.
- [7] C. J. Gillon, C. Baker, R. Ly, E. Balzani, B. W. Brunton, M. Schottdorf, S. Ghosh, and N. Dehghani, “Open Data In Neurophysiology: Advancements, Solutions & Challenges,” *eNeuro* **12** no. 11, (Nov., 2025) .
- [8] C. Curto and N. Sanderson, “Topological Neuroscience: Linking Circuits to Function,” *Annual Review of Neuroscience* **48** no. Volume 48, 2025, (July, 2025) 491–518.
- [9] A. E. Sizemore, J. E. Phillips-Cremins, R. Ghrist, and D. S. Bassett, “The importance of the whole: Topological data analysis for the network neuroscientist,” *Network Neuroscience* **3** no. 3, (July, 2019) 656–673.
- [10] G. Singh, F. Memoli, T. Ishkhanov, G. Sapiro, G. Carlsson, and D. L. Ringach, “Topological analysis of population activity in visual cortex,” *Journal of Vision* **8** no. 8, (June, 2008) 11.
- [11] R. J. Gardner, E. Hermansen, M. Pachitariu, Y. Burak, N. A. Baas, B. A. Dunn, M.-B. Moser, and E. I. Moser, “Toroidal topology of population activity in grid cells,” *Nature* **602** no. 7895, (Feb., 2022) 123–128.
- [12] C. Curto and V. Itskov, “Cell Groups Reveal Structure of Stimulus Space,” *PLOS Computational Biology* **4** no. 10, (Oct., 2008) e1000205.

- [13] R. Chaudhuri, B. Gerçek, B. Pandey, A. Peyrache, and I. Fiete, “The intrinsic attractor manifold and population dynamics of a canonical cognitive circuit across waking and sleep,” *Nature Neuroscience* **22** no. 9, (Sept., 2019) 1512–1520.
- [14] L. Petrucco, H. Lavian, Y. K. Wu, F. Svara, V. Štíh, and R. Portugues, “Neural dynamics and architecture of the heading direction circuit in zebrafish,” *Nature Neuroscience* **26** no. 5, (May, 2023) 765–773.
- [15] M. G. Perich, D. Narain, and J. A. Gallego, “A neural manifold view of the brain,” *Nature Neuroscience* **28** no. 8, (Aug., 2025) 1582–1597.
- [16] K. Friston, “Does predictive coding have a future?” *Nature Neuroscience* **21** no. 8, (Aug., 2018) 1019–1021.
- [17] T. Marques, J. Nguyen, G. Fioreze, and L. Petreanu, “The functional organization of cortical feedback inputs to primary visual cortex,” *Nature Neuroscience* **21** no. 5, (May, 2018) 757–764.
- [18] G. Carlsson, V. de Silva, and D. Morozov, “Zigzag persistent homology and real-valued functions,” in *Proceedings of the Twenty-Fifth Annual Symposium on Computational Geometry*, SCG ’09, pp. 247–256. Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, June, 2009.
- [19] M. D. Wilkinson, M. Dumontier, I. J. Aalbersberg, G. Appleton, M. Axton, A. Baak, N. Blomberg, J.-W. Boiten, L. B. da Silva Santos, P. E. Bourne, J. Bouwman, A. J. Brookes, T. Clark, M. Crosas, I. Dillo, O. Dumon, S. Edmunds, C. T. Evelo, R. Finkers, A. Gonzalez-Beltran, A. J. G. Gray, P. Groth, C. Goble, J. S. Grethe, J. Heringa, P. A. C. ’t Hoen, R. Hooft, T. Kuhn, R. Kok, J. Kok, S. J. Lusher, M. E. Martone, A. Mons, A. L. Packer, B. Persson, P. Rocca-Serra, M. Roos, R. van Schaik, S.-A. Sansone, E. Schultes, T. Sengstag, T. Slater, G. Strawn, M. A. Swertz, M. Thompson, J. van der Lei, E. van Mulligen, J. Velterop, A. Waagmeester, P. Wittenburg, K. Wolstencroft, J. Zhao, and B. Mons, “The FAIR guiding principles for scientific data management and stewardship,” *Scientific Data* **3** no. 1, (Mar., 2016) 160018.